

Increasing rice production by using terpenoids

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The introduction of semidwarf tropical indica plant type varieties has substantially improved rice production. We are attempting to raise the yields above the present 10 t/ha potential by using terpenoids and their synthetic derivatives as plant growth regulators.

PR106 seeds were treated with solutions of known and recently synthesized terpenoids/essential oils.

Effect of growth regulators on rice yield, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment		1981 kharif		1983 kharif	
		Yield (t/ha)	Percent of control	Yield (t/ha)	Percent of control
Essential oil from <i>Cyperus scariosus</i>	100 ppm	9.9	106	6.0	111
	200 ppm	—	—	5.4	102
Zerumbone	100 ppm	10.5	112	5.5	103
	200 ppm	—	—	5.8	108
C ₁₆ -Guaianolide	100 ppm	10.0	107	5.7	107
	200 ppm	—	—	5.7	106
Control		9.3	100	5.3	100

Solutions were prepared by dissolving the desired quantity of the compounds in small quantity of alcohol and then adding warm water to the desired volume. Seeds were soaked in this

solution for 24 h. Five-wk-old seedlings from treated and untreated (control) seeds were planted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 1981 and 1983 kharif, and yield was recorded (see table). □

Efficiency of P fertilizers as determined by IR20 grain yield

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We conducted a pot experiment to determine the relative efficiency of P fertilizers as determined by rice grain yield. Soil was alluvial with low Olsen's P (8 kg/ha), 950 ppm P-fixing capacity, pH 6.3, and CEC 54 meq/100 g. The experiment was in a complete randomized design with two replications. Coated and uncoated water-soluble P fertilizers diammonium phosphate (DAP), monoammonium phosphate (MAP), single superphosphate (SSP), and insoluble rock phosphate were applied. P was applied at 26.19, 39.29, and 52.39 kg/ha with 120 kg adjusted total N/ha.

Relative efficiency of different P fertilizers as determined by rice grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

P fertilizer (total P content %)	Grain yield (g/pot)			
	26.19 kg P/ha	39.29 kg P/ha	52.39 kg P/ha	Mean
DAP (20.9)	22.3	24.4	24.8	23.8
MAP (23.6)	17.9	18.4	18.7	18.3
SSP (8.9)	20.6	22.2	22.6	21.8
Coated DAP (10.7)	22.6	23.8	24.6	23.7
Coated MAP (12.1)	17.9	18.7	19.4	18.6
Coated SSP (5.2)	21.3	22.0	22.2	21.8
Rock phosphate (14.8)	15.6	16.8	17.2	16.5
Coated rock phosphate (6.1)	15.7	16.2	16.3	16.1
Mean	19.23	20.31	20.74	20.09
			CD 5%	
			Sources of P	0.54
			Levels of P	0.20
			Interaction	ns

Water-soluble P sources increased rice grain yield more efficiently than insoluble P (see table). DAP gave the maximum yield followed by SSP and MAP. Coated

and uncoated treatments produced similarly. Increased P application enhanced grain production. Interaction effects were insignificant. □

Varietal tolerance for bentazon in direct-seeded lowland rice

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Controlling rice weeds with selective post-emergence herbicides is gaining importance in direct-seeded lowland rice. We evaluated the effect of postemergence herbicide application on weed growth and grain yield of direct-seeded lowland IR36, Mahsuri, and T141 in wet season. The

Effect of bentazon on grain yield of 3 rice cultivars and weed mortality, Orissa, India.

Treatment	IR36			Mahsuri			T141		
	Weeds ^a (no./m ²)	Weed wt ^b (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weeds ^a (no./m ²)	Weed wt ^b (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weeds ^a (no./m ²)	Weed wt ^b (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Bentazon @ 2 kg/ha	97	108	2.6	75	66	3.0	66	49	2.0
Bentazon @ 2 kg/ha + 2,4-D @ 1 kg/ha	58	48	2.9	52	39	3.3	40	27	2.4
Two hand weedings at 25 and 45 d after seeding	37	21	3.2	32	20	3.4	29	18	2.2
Untreated and unweeded control	412	217	1.1	277	169	1.6	219	104	1.8

^a60 d after sowing, ^b90 d after sowing.

field trial was in a split-plot design with four replications. Two kg bentazon/ha was applied alone and in combination with 1.0 kg amine salt of 2,4-D/ha as a directed spray 15 d after rice germinated.

Weed flora in the experimental field was 60-70% annual sedges (*Cyperus iria* L., *C. diffomis* L., *Fimbristylis miliacea* (L) Vahl, *Scirpus acutus* Muhl), 15-20% annual broadleaf weeds (*Aeschynomene indica* Linn, *Ludwigia parviflora* Rosb., *Cyanotis cucullata* Kunth, *Monochoria*

vaginalis Presl), and 10-15% annual grasses (*Echinochloa crus-galli* (L) Beauv., *Eragrostis cilianensis* (L) Beauv.).

Bentazon treatments did not damage any rice but IR36. Parts of IR36 leaves turned yellow-brown the day after bentazon treatment, but the discoloration disappeared 5-7 d later.

Weed control efficiency was assessed 60 and 90 d after sowing. Bentazon + 2,4-D controlled weeds in T141 and Mahsuri significantly better than in IR36,

perhaps because T141 and Mahsuri form a thicker canopy more quickly than semi-dwarf IR36. Weed weight differed for different rice varieties, but interaction between herbicide treatment and variety was not significant.

Bentazon + 2,4-D gave significantly higher grain yield in T141 over hand weeding and bentazon alone (see table). Results with bentazon would be different if grasses were the predominant weed species. □

Machinery development and testing

Husk-fired rice parboiling unit developed

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We developed a husk-fired, 0.5-t capacity rice parboiling unit that is suitable for use by farmers and small rice mills. It uses steam parboiling.

The unit consists of a 1.2- × 1.2-m galvanized iron drum that is separated horizontally into 2 chambers by perforated G. I. sheet. The lower 25-cm chamber is the hot water chamber and the upper 95-cm compartment is the steam chamber. A 7.5-cm-diam G. I. vertical pipe is at the center with lateral 2.5-cm pipes welded to it in triplets at 15-cm intervals. The unit is mounted over a husk-fired furnace constructed of country bricks and clay mortar. A 20-cm water

Cracks during milling of IR20 raw rice and parboiled rice.

column is maintained in the hot-water chamber and water-soaked rice is fed into the steam chamber. The unit is emptied

through the exit door.

The first batch of rice takes 25-30 min to be parboiled, and subsequent batches take 15-20 min. Traditional country parboiling takes 70-90 min/batch. With this unit, parboiling cost per tonne is 17% of that in the country method because of higher fuel utilization efficiency.

The figure compares percent breakage during milling for different parboiling methods at constant drying temperatures, but varying drying time. Using the steam parboiler, the crack percentage has been reduced to 8-12% from 40-45% for the traditional method. Bran oil content was 4-6% more than with the traditional method.

This parboiling method eliminates the dark color and undesirable smell of rice that is common with the traditional method, and eliminates development of any mycotoxins. □

Announcements

Pakistan names two IRTP entries as varieties

The Government of Pakistan recently approved rice varieties IET4094 (CR156-5021) and IR2053-261-2-3 for cultivation in Sind Province. The varieties were received from IRRI through the International Rice Testing Program and tested under local conditions for several years.

IET4094 was named Dokri Rice 82 (DR82) and is expected to replace the currently grown variety IR6. DR82 is high yielding, matures early, and has better grain quality than IR6. IR2053 was named Dokri Rice 83 (DR83). It is early maturing and is suitable for late transplanting in Aug. Until now, no variety has been available for Aug transplanting. □

New IRRI publications

The following new IRRI publications are available for purchase from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines:

Field problems of tropical rice
(Spanish edition)
Organic matter and rice